

An Appraisal of the Dynamics that Obligated Christian Influence on Tiv Religious Culture in 18th to 21st Centuries

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Abstract

The advent of Christianity has influenced the life of Nigerian, particularly the Tiv people of Central Nigeria in so many ways. Christianity has been accused of coming with depraved intentions to invade the traditional religious practices and cultural value of the Tiv people. Using comparative approach, this study undertakes to unravel the factors that necessitated these influences of Christianity on Tiv cultural values in the 21st century. Historical, descriptive and expository methods were used and data were gathered from both primary and secondary sources. Findings from the study revealed that, the advent of Christianity has however caused more damage than just the invasion of Tiv traditional religious practices and cultural values. While it did not seek to undermine the social and cultural practices that had been in existence, it rather destroyed the Tiv traditional religious culture. As a result of this, so many aspects of changes have been affected on Tiv religious cultural values. The study concluded with the recommendation that, all over Africa today most especially in central Nigeria, there is the move towards cultural revival and as such, it is the right time for the Tiv people to wake up from their slumber and denounced those negative persuasions infringed on them in the past that, their culture is inferior and barbaric and they are to accept foreign values and ways of life. Also that, the traditional council should rise up to her responsibilities to preserve the Tiv cultural heritage and cherished traditional code of conduct that is systematically eroding away to be taught at all levels of education especially in Tiv Land to enable the younger generation know about their well-organised cultural heritage and the need to sustain the positive values. In this capacity, there should be much emphasis on Christianising Tiv culture and traditions.

Keywords: Dynamics, Christianity, Tiv Culture, Traditions Values and Cultural Revival

Introduction

Nigeria, like many other Africans states is a country of diverse cultures, traditions and faiths. It is a pluralistic society and of all the diverse elements and religion has proven to be the most sensitive and the one that has often led to hatred and division.¹ Religion has made their impacts felt in all aspect of human existence. It is worthy of note that, Nigeria is a religious nation and all the people in high and low positions profess one religion or another and their anxious to take their religion anywhere they go. This act therefore showed the value of Nigerians on religion.

It is discovered that there have been systematic changes in almost all aspects of life, be it socially and culturally values of Tiv Religion, since the advent of Christianity in Tiv land. As a result, modern settlement patterns are found in Tiv land and the mode of dressing of the Tiv has changed. The true traditional religion of the Tiv has been abandoned with everyone prefers to become a Christianity. English language is considered even in the local gathering in villages by the elites. In fact, everything about traditional is regarded as old fashioned and barbaric.

Considering the above therefore, this study is poised to unravel the factors that necessitated these influences of Christianity on Tiv cultural values in the 21st century and the response of the Tiv people to this religion since its advent, as well as their present image in this religion. This study under take to harmonise both

religions by eclecticising their good elements in order to produce a better and a well-organised cultural for the Tiv people of central Nigeria. Thus, the purpose of this study is to investigate those phases through which Christianity had influenced on the Tiv religious cultural in the 18th to 21st centuries.

The Origin and Essential Nature of Christian Religion

The quest by man to come nearer to God for worship as the supreme creator started long ago. However, Downes says “Christianity is relatively younger compared with the course of mankind”.² For Richard McBrien, Christianity is to be understood as the community of those who on the ground of the resurrection of Christ acquired the kingdom of God and whose life is determined by this expectation.³ Here, Christianity which follows Christ’s Mission to the world should also engage in following Christ’s service of the world. Biblically, Christianity came into being during the death of Jesus Christ around AD 33 in the Jewish city of Jerusalem. By this understanding, Idahosa puts it that, “Christianity has its roots deeply back into the history and religion of Israel.”⁴ This confirmed in Jesus’ statement, salvation is from the Jews (John 4:22). Jesus Christ, the founder of Christianity in one of his sermons told Peter that “you are Peter and on this rock, I will build my Church” (Matthew 16:18). This therefore, marked the beginning of Christian Church on earth.

The Grolier international Encyclopedia defines Christianity as the religion of about a billion people whose belief system is centered on the person and teachings of Jesus Christ.⁵ According to the above view, Jesus Christ of Nazareth was and is the messiah or Christ promised by God in the prophecies of old Testament, by his life death and resurrection, he freed those who believe in him from their sinful state and made them recipients of God’s saving grace. Christians are therefore, the believers in the teachings of Jesus Christ or have been baptised in a Christian Church. According to Joseph Omoregbe, Christianity is a Christo-Centric Religion; this he meant that Jesus Christ is its focal point. Jesus Christ is seen as God who is for us men and our salvation, come down from heaven, and unless one believes in him, he cannot be saved.⁶

To Gbenda, Christianity is essentially living the life of Christ and following the path he laid for salvation of mankind.⁷ Christianity is a monotheistic religion; it believes in the existence of one God but accommodates the idea of three persons in one God, and the idea of God having a divine son (Jesus). Christianity as a religion which has Jesus as the focal point has the followings as its ethical teachings: It preaches peace on earth that men should be in harmony with one another. It preaches love and emphasises the fact that God’s love is demonstrated through love for one another. It teaches obedient to constituted authority; it emphasises social services to one another and also teaches humility.⁸

Christianity has the Bible as its Holy Scriptures and this include the Old and New Testament, which are the collections of the early Christian writing proclaiming Jesus as Lord and saviour. Arising in the Jewish Milieu of the first century Palestine, Christianity quickly spread through the Mediterranean World and in the 14th century became the official religion of the Roman Empire and here is Nigeria, history had it that, Christianity is the major religion with the highest number of adherent measuring more than half of the total population of Nigeria.⁹

The Origin and Essential Nature of African Religion

Religion according to Anyacho is derived from two Latin words *religio* meaning sacredness, piety, or fear of the supernatural and *religale* which means to hold together, to bind or fasten.¹⁰ Ekarika considered religion as an act that one has carefully observed, chosen and bound to, in worship and loving care.¹¹ Religion therefore denotes man’s experience, awareness, attitude, recognition, conception, and understanding of the existence of the supernatural or the multiplicity of spiritual beings and his relationship or interaction with them.¹²

African Religion like Tiv religion has no founder; it grew out of people’s culture. It has no sacred scripture. It is handed down from one generation to another, from a father to the son.¹³ To Joseph Omorogbe, to understand African traditional religion, one need to understand the people involved, this is because, it is rooted in African experience and environment.¹⁴ According to Mbiti, African religion is a monotheistic religion. It is a Liberal

monotheism which allows God to be approached through subordinate beings who are his servants. These are divinities that occupy the place of angels in Christianity and Islam.¹⁵

Africans do not see themselves confronted with a choice between worshipping God or divinities since it is God Himself that they Worship through these divinities. Traditional Africans are highly connected with their beliefs and culture such that their thinking and actions as well as their social relations are guided and directed by the gods of the land. These gods and deities ensure that offenders are adequately punished.¹⁶ Based on this understanding Ode asserts that, for Africans, morality is part and parcel of life. Therefore, there is no distinction between morality and religion in African religion.

African traditional religion in Shishima's understanding contains rules of life and basic moral and social virtues like honesty, purity, loyalty, courage, respect for elders and authority and also sacred ceremonies.¹⁷ These show the people hope, aspirations, and relationship to the Supreme Being to Makozi, it is African religion that gives its followers a sense of security in life. It provides for them answers and directions in life. People are not willing to abound on it quickly, even when they are converted to other religion, they still mix their traditional religion with the one they had converted to.¹⁸ Having seen the perceptive nature of African religion in all aspect of lives, Mbiti say thus, "the traditional religion which consists of a variety of localised religions practices and beliefs are presently defining in institutional vigor and importance, given way to Islam and Christianity."¹⁶

Tiv Religious Beliefs and Practices

The word Tiv according to Atoato has three interrelated meanings: (i) The name of the patriarchal ancestor believes to be progenitor of the Tiv people, (ii) The collection of all persons who trace their origin and descent from (i) above, (iii) The most obvious cultural expression (language) of (ii) above. Thus, Tiv can be understood as referring to a person and cultures and items identified or associated with the people, for example, Tivland, Tiv dance, Tiv architecture, Tiv cloth, Tiv yam and so on.²⁰

According to Ajiki, the term Tiv refers to the people, their language as well as their progeny. One of the popular stories about the origin of the Tiv people was that they were driven from their shadowy home beyond the waters, somewhere in the east by an impeccable enemy called the "Ugenyi" in a head long fight from the enemy who were pursuing them, they come to a body of water which they could not cross. While considering empirical information which can be extracted from their writings the wild appearance and fragmentary polity of the Tiv and their migration led them to conclude that the present Tiv see their origin and oneness as well as their ethnic consciousness in Tiv himself who had to sons: Ipusu and Ichongo.²¹

Historically, there is no concise documented research that states categorically the exact place where the Tiv originated. According to Gbenda, the origin and migration of the Tiv people into the Benue valley is shrouded in mystery.²² Bur observed that the task of studying the origin, character and development of ethnic groups in Nigeria would continue to be challenging to the historians and other scholars since oral relations varies and most tribes do not agree on the issues.²³ The problem of ascertaining the exact origin of the Tiv is captured by Gbenda that "the early and modern writers have often contradicted themselves about Tiv origin, migrations and settlement, the contradictions are due to the different versions of Tiv oral traditions."²⁴

However, some scholars traced Tiv origin from Bantu of southern Africa through the mountainous region of Cameroon republic to the Benue valley which dated about 16th and 17th centuries ago.²⁵ Researches like Downes (93), Akiga (203), Abraham (40), Dzurgba (27) and so many others who maintained that the Tiv originated from a mountainous and hilly region located in the republic of Cameroon as observed by Bohannan, "Tiv say that their original home was a hill which the call far to the south-East of their present location." According to Gbor, the Tiv originated from a man called Tiv whose father was Takunku and Aliwe his wife. Takuluku and his wife Aliwe gave birth to Tiv. Tiv later married Ayaaya and produced four children. Gbe, Ichongo, Ipusu and Anadendem who was the only girl and a cripple. The story continued that Gbe the eldest son left his parents to unknown place while Anadendem died without an issue, leaving Ichongo and Ipusu. These two got married and produced children who constitute the Tiv nation.²⁶

Tiv religion is therefore called *Kwagh-Aondo* and is the centred on the belief in Aondo (God), Tsav, (Supernatural forces), Akombo (Divinities), Adzov (Spirits) and Uter Mbayiase (Ancestors). Aondo (God) is the Supreme Being, the creator of everything including man. For the Tiv, Aondo (God) is not an object but a being with personality attributes. Therefore, Aondo (God) can be angry and express his anger in his rear of thunder and spitting of storms.²⁷ other scholars like Akiga (2003), Dzurgba (2007), Bohannan (1995), Moti and Wegh (2001), wrote on the Tiv believe in Aondo (God). Bohannan's on the other hand considered Aondo (God) as a Otiose god, who created the world and later withdrew from it to be ran by persons, spirit and other force which Aondo (God) has created.²⁸ This explains the Tiv believe that Aondo (God) once lived near man and commended with him but due to carelessness and disobedience has left to the sky.²⁹ Akosu opines that the Tiv do not deal with Aondo (God) day by day as the nearly forces of (supernatural forces), Adzov (spirits), and Akombo (divinities). He is only called upon during the moment of intense crisis and trouble.³⁰ The invocation of Aondo (God) according to Akiga was done by the elders of the Tiv community. Accepting this view, Gbenda explain that "the Tiv people call their ancestors (Mbayiase or The Tiv believed that Aondo speaks to them through their ancestors. In case of impending danger or calamity, the traditional Tiv, often call on God of their ancestors like Aondo (God) of Gbayange, Ityevajir, Ikeretar and Abaverjua."³¹

Apart from Aondo (God) and Mbayiase (Ancestors), the Tiv also believed in the reality of Tsav (supernatural forces) and Akombo (divinities). Adegba is with the view that Tsav is witchcraft while Mbatsav refers to the people that practice witchcraft.³² Igbum on the other hand, considered Tsav as something that enables one to have great influence over others.³³ Akiga has seen Tsav as the power by which a man can achieve something that is beyond his normal faculties to accomplish.³⁴ It is also a superior knowledge which is associated with dark practices thereby giving the possessor an extra ordinary possession of power and influence.³⁵ In the same vein, is regarded as a mystical power and an aspect of personality which makes someone to dominate a particular situation, to change events the way he wants, to command obedience and attract royalty.³⁶

Investigation reveals that the Tiv classified as benevolent (good) and malevolent (bad) Tsav depending on the possessor and not Tsav itself. It could be used for good deals as well as to cause trouble and destruction in the traditional community.³⁷ In order to curtail the malevolent or negative practice of Tsav in Tiv land, there existed numerous anti-witchcraft movements like Hoyo or Dankol of (1920), Ijov of (1912), Budeli (1930), Ivase (1920), Haakaa or Naakaa (1934), Inyambuan (1939), Korchan cult (1980), Nyamor (2001), Nyamkwase (2001) and Igbe (Anti- witchcraft masquerade).³⁸

Akombo (Plural) or Kombo (singular) are the mystical forces represented in cubic emblems. Akombo is a neutral force which is productive and destructive in nature.³⁹ The Tiv belief system is such that every component of life has behind it a non-human power called Akombo. The magical ability of Akombo provides for every eventuality of life and for the control of the unseen forces as well as for protection against the vengeance or retribution of dangerous forces which if not treated properly, could let loose their particular properties. This view is backed by scholars like Wegh, (1998), Akiga (2003), Downes (1997) the Akombo have the unseen power to deal with human problems.⁴⁰

The reality of Adzov in Tiv religions worldview cannot be overemphasised since Tiv believe that Adzov are spiritual beings that live and interact with the people. Moti and Wegh explained that "Adzov are not commonly seen, identified or recognised by ordinary human eyes. In some cases, Adzov may decide to appear in grotesque shapes which could only be seen by those who have special sight for recognising them." The Tiv occupy the Benue valley and share boundary with other tribes as noted by Gbenda that, the Tiv people are bounded in the North by the Arago and Lafia peoples of Nasarawa state and plateau State. Along the southern boundaries are Obudu and Ogoja peoples of Cross River states. In the East, they are intermingled with the Jukun in Wukari and Chamba of Taraba State. Also, they are bordered to the East by Cameroon while in the western axis there Igede and Idomas of Benue State.⁴¹

Torkula explains that the Tiv are mainly located in Benue State with a population of over two million (1999 census figure). The land the Tiv occupy stretches out on both sides of River Benue and covers an area of

about 30,000 square kilometers. Most of it lies 2440 meters above sea level. Tiv land lies roughly within latitude $6^{\circ} 3'$ North and it is a grass land. On the other hand, the area occupied by the Tiv lies in the Benue trough of Nigeria's middle belt zone, stretching from $6^{\circ} 3'N$ to $8^{\circ}N$ and from $8^{\circ} E$ to $10^{\circ}E$. The Tiv are found predominantly in Benue State but large Tiv population is found in Nassarawa and Taraba states of Nigeria." The Tiv land enjoys a moderate rainfall with two distinctive seasons, the dry and raining seasons which characterised the region under a tropical climate.⁴⁴

Phases through which Christianity Influenced Tiv Religious Culture in 18th - 21st Centuries

The advent of Christianity has influenced the life of Nigerian, particularly the Tiv people of Central Nigeria in so many ways. The following are some of areas through which Christianity has influenced on Tiv religious culture from 18th to 21st centuries. These include:

1. Socio-Cultural Organisation: In the Tiv traditional community, the people live together in a large compound, which made up of thatched houses with Ate (common meeting place) at the centre where Orya (head of the compound) normally sits. Akiga observed that, "the head of the family is accustomed to sit with his wife and his guests, and when he makes beer, it is here that the people sit and drink."⁴⁵ It should be noted that a traditional Tiv man needs to marry many wives and produce many children. Storytelling and folktales (u tan kwagh alom) also form the Tiv social life. Stories and folktales are told to the younger ones and women for the purpose of inculcating moral norms and values, "There are numerous folktales in Tiv land and the people are known for that. More often than not, folktales are acted with much energy and relevance to the people."⁴⁶ According to East, these stories are told under moon light after the day hard labor is centered on the Hare (the wisest animals) and other cultures. Some stories talk about spirits like Adzov and Mbakur.⁴⁷

The Tiv are hospitable, accommodating and generous in arms. They eat in unionism even with strangers and visitors. Despite these attributes, the Tiv find it difficult to progress in life. Many Tiv people view this as due to jealousy common among themselves. Kwav (age group) and Igba (maternal relations) are other vital social platform among the people.⁴⁸ These two groups contribute greatly to the religious, economic and social wellbeing of their members and relations respectively.

Also worthy of note is the Tiv traditional dance (Amaa) festivals. Segun asserts that "In Africa, cultural dance is life and life is dance because life is beautiful, dance is beautiful. Dance is pivotal to which all human activities revolved."⁴⁹ Traditionally, the Tiv often organised Amaa (Dance) for young men and during kwase kuhan (Marriage). Some dance festivals are both social and religious in nature. These are Ibamegh, Ivom, kwagh-hir and so on. The Tiv traditional musical instruments used during the dance festival include indyer or ilu (wooden drum), kwen, agbande among others.⁵⁰ On the occasion of Amaa (Dance) festival, the organiser would invite his Kwav (age group); Igba (maternal relations) and his Ityo (council of elders). The person who brews the Amaa (Dance) festival would ride on Inyinya (Horse) and sometimes may enter Nyamtsuam masquerade as a symbol of Shagba (prestige) and freedom from ikpindi (flesh-bebt).⁵¹

2. Political Organisation: According to Dzurgba, leadership in Tiv traditional society is gerontocracy in nature. Gerontocracy is leadership by old age or the elderly. The Tiv system of government is quasi democratic in practice as it is made up of gerontocratic representatives from families which constitute the Ya (compound) ye-Ngyor, (kindred council) and the Ityo (clan council). The basis for selection of the representative is on the ground of old age. The oldest men formed the quasi democratic government and assume political, social, economic and religious powers.⁵² Agreeing with the above views, Denga added that; the first political structure in Tiv traditional government is Ya (compound) with Orya (oldest man) as the head. He chaired the compound council; he has the power or responsibility of settling marital case as well as land, political, social, economic and religious disputes in union members of the family which make up a given compound during the council meeting.⁵³

The traditional Tiv society was completely egalitarian. There was no central authority. They had no king so every man was ruler of his own house. They live in compounds administered by the oldest man. Many compounds formed clans and districts that were variously divided and sub-divided the elders of the various clans

and districts (Ityar) met and discussed issues of those levels and arrived at democratic decision that bound their sections. If an issue involved the whole ethnic group the elders of the various sections and district met took a decision.⁵⁴ This situation obtained until 1946 when the colonialist established a Tiv central authority by creating the office of a paramount ruler. The paramount ruler (Tor Tiv) lives and administers the people in Gboko, their headquarters town, which was built in 1932. Ascendancy to the Tor Tiv throne is not hereditary.

3. Tiv Worldview: Worldview is a concept that has varying dimensions and perspectives. “A people’s worldview may be defined as the complex of their beliefs and attitudes concerning the origin, nature, structure of the universe and interaction of its beings with particular reference to man.”⁵⁵ Another author noted that a worldview is a body of beliefs about the universe which are common among members of any society and existentially demonstrated in their value system, such as their philosophies of life, social conduct and morality, folk-lore’s, myths, rites and rituals, norms, rules, ideas, cognitive mappings theologies and so on.⁵⁶

The emphasis in this view is on the elements of infraction and connectedness which underpins all worldview. Everything is linked. There is an analogical link of all the beings within a particular worldview. In the context Tiv culture and religion; worldview is the unified picture of the world cosmos, understanding and interpretation of things in their environment. Worldview also includes attitude to life, now and after life, what things are worth striving to attain in life and the place of man in creation.⁵⁷ On the structure of the African worldview, Idowu mentioned the Supreme Being, deities, spiritual beings. Scholars have maintained that the Tiv people being semi-bantu have a very simple structure of worldview, which includes the Supreme Being, spirit of the dead, and magic.⁵⁸ As such, their worldview differs significantly from the other West African societies.

Gbenda subscribe to the view that the Tiv people are semi-Bantu but denied the Tiv people’s worldview is a three-tier structure at it is generally held. He went further to say that the correct structure of Tiv traditional worldview includes Aondo (God), or (man), Akombo (mystical forces), Tsav (witchcraft), mbatsav (witches), ancestor and imborivungu (cultic emblem).⁵⁹ God or the Supreme Being is known among the Tiv as Aondo. The assertion by scholars that the Tiv have a vague idea of God is erroneous. There is no ethnic group in Africa that doesn’t have a notion of God.⁶⁰

In a way, worldview is usually unique to a person or a group of people. Thus a people can use their worldview to explain the attitudinal orientation towards certain happening peculiar to them alone. The Tiv outlook on the world can be discerned from the different aspects of the Tiv people’s way of life. Some of these aspects are those dealing with their religious values and customs, their notion of personhood, their view of the individual as against the community, and their value of human life. In this perspective, Rubingh succinctly describes the Tiv worldview as one that “was complex and effective, for it organised all of life and encompassed the individual, the tribe, the land and the far reaches of the universe in one majestic totality: kinship bound man to make and structured the compound, the idea of far bound man his lands, the concept of Tsav and Akombo provided a union of man with the cosmic powers.”⁶¹

This Tiv worldview is taken to mean as defined by Achebe, “the totality of each person’s assumptions involving his beliefs, concepts, attitudes and values which tends to give explanation to everything that This Tiv worldview is taken to means as deterred by Achebe, “The totality of each person’s assumptions involving his beliefs, concepts, attitudes and values which lends to give explanation to everything that happens.”⁶² On the whole, therefore, the worldview of traditional Africans in general and Tiv in particular is deeply religious. Hence the nature of Tiv traditional moral system can best understood from the background of Tiv worldview. No aspect of their social and individual life is not understood religiously, the Tiv people believe in a High God, Aondo, who is the creator of all things including moral values. Thus Tiv cultural values are determined by religions standard.

4. Tiv Cultural Values: Tiv people have a rich cultural heritage. Their way of life is hinged on the matrix of their religio-cultural heritage which is passed down from one generation to the other. Life in traditional Tiv society like other African traditional societies has certain traditional norms and values which they extol and uphold. These values originated from their common experiences which are peculiar to their own milieu as people of a given geographical area and culture.

Life in Tiv traditional society was fairly well organised around such social values and ideas as: Respect for elders, Respect for life, Honesty, Chastity, Hard work, Justice, Truthfulness, Decent and Dignified behaviour, Humility, Communalism, Hospitality, Good Name. Integrity and Public interest rather than selfishness.⁶³ Human actions and expectations are premised on the internalised values of the Tiv society which simply means doing things the way (Aondo) God created human beings to think, behave and act as was right passed onto them by past generations.

The entire Tiv traditional society is wholly religious and since cultural values are tied to religion, the Tiv people before modernisation (coming of Christianity) maintain high moral standards. Tiv cultural values in the context of this study will be used interchangeably with morality and is applied to mean a set of social rules norms intended to guide the conduct of the Tiv people. The rules and norms emerge from and are anchored in the people's belief system about right and wrong conduct, good and bad character. Cultural values are therefore used to refer to those social and moral behaviours dealing with both right and wrong. This reflects not only the Horizontal dimension in which those moral elements that serve as links between man and man in society are considered but also the vertical perspective in which the conditions of relationship between God and man are highlighted.

Tiv cultural values are noted by Gbenda is like that of Africans and is based purely on their traditions, customs, norms and prohibitions of actions which one ought to do and those things considered bad to be avoided. Tiv values are expressed in the norms, which regulate relationship between individuals and social groups. There are sanctions or condemnations attached to going contrary to the observance of the norms.⁶⁴ Tiv values are seen to be more spiritual than nature. They like other Africans belief that their morality emerges from religions and is given them by God whom they called Aondo from the very beginning of the world. Tiv morality is referred to as Gbaaondo. Msue noted that Gbaaondo stands for the Truth, Justice, Unity, Brotherhood and that which is truly right.

Supporting this view Quarcoopome audaciously and succinctly wrote that, moral values are part and parcel of religion and that both of them are dovetailed and inseparable. He put it thus; in West African traditional Religion (the Tiv of central Nigeria inclusive) morality is the fruit of religion. This means that in the traditional context there is no such distinction between cultural values and religion because there is close relationship between religions are moral life. The social and moral ordinances are the injunctions of God who had himself, instituted them.⁶⁵

Further support to this view come from Gbenda who asserts that, in this ideology, when good or right conduct is maintained in society, there is good relationship with the sacred, the source of goodness itself and who demand such from man. In Tiv society, right actions promote equilibrium in the created order. Negative actions disrupt the created orderliness and breed sufferings and sickness, among others. A valued Tiv person is identified by his hospitality, love concern for common good, mercifulness, sympathy, respect, peace, justice, objectivity, forgiveness and impartiality. The Tiv people generally frown at greed, selfishness, injustice, theft, criminal activities, poisoning, killing, cruelty, cowardice; disrespect, arrogance, fornication, adultery and all other evil vices are condemned.⁶⁶ From the foregoing, it is palpable that Tiv cultural values emerge from religion and any devoid of cultural values is in danger of being superstition and not religion because religion and cultural values are inseparable.

5. Tiv Moral Values: Moral values in this context of study can be used inter-changeably with morality is applied to mean, as defined by Gyekye as a set of social rules and norms intended to guide the conduct of people in a society. The rules and norms emerge from and are anchored in people's belief about right and wrong conduct and good are bad character.⁶⁷ Generally, in every human society, there is a set pattern of conduct concerning ideas about good behaviours and about what is considered bad or wrong. This position was supported by Gbenda that, Tiv people of central Nigeria not been an exception, have a great deal of diversity of moral values held by the people from other ethnic groups⁶⁸. He went further to explain that, the moral conduct of a person is bound to affect others, positively or negatively.

Dzurgba recognises two categories of action in Tiv society, which constitute their morality. The first one is *ieren idedoo* good action and the second one *ieren ibo* refers to evil action. In the plural form there are *aeren a dedoo* and *aeren a bo*-meaning good/right and evil/wrong actions.⁶⁹ Similarly, this is expressed Anshi as “u” translated as something good while what is bad is regarded as *u ho* the knowledge of what is good (*dedoo*) is included within the general experience of the people.⁷⁰ This is to explain that the yard stick is thus what is generally accepted as *doo* (good). It is in this regard that some families are regarded as good (*doo*) people on account of their forbears who had lived exemplary life.

In the same perspective, children of a sorcerer will always be regarded as bad people. This is because morality among the Tiv people like any other African nationality is based purely on their traditional customs, norms and prohibitions which one ought to do and those things considered bad to be avoided. Tiv morality is exposed in the norms like love, fidelity and unity, which regulated relationships between individuals and social groups. Given that morality is built on individuals and societal relationships, Nzomiwu states that; in African societies, interdictions and norms which are community centered with community solidarity at heart. Certain actions or virtues are encouraged because they foster relationship within society.⁷¹ The understanding is that, there must be a custodian who would see to it that such objectives are accomplished as well as its compliance. The emphasis is also that such people must be of good moral standards.

In Tivland, the promoters and custodian of moral values are *mbavesen* (elders) among others. They are also custodians of ancestral blessings. When elders of respectful families come together, they constitute a corporate body called *ityo* (council of elders). Their meeting in the daytime has its correspondence in the invisible world where important matters are discussed and decisions implemented in the daytime. The elders have power to decide on one's life span and death.⁷²

6. Tiv Contact with the Western World: Western culture, though not bad in itself but alien to Tiv culture created unfavorable conditions which largely transformed the long-cherished Tiv traditional values. Tiv society therefore metamorphosed to an injudicious copying trend inimical to what was known on moral values in Tiv land. The following has under-gone dramatic change to the detriment of the entire Tiv society. The exploration of the African coast by the Portuguese in the 19th century was accompanied by the arrival of the European missionaries in African soil. Their arrival found functioning societies in which people lived reasonably prosperous and happy lives. According to Bujo, most of the Europeans who came to Africa at the beginning of colonial period did not do so with the idea of helping or civilising the black people but for the reason of self-interest.⁷³

The Tiv came into contact with European culture during the colonial period. During November 1907 to spring 1908, an expedition of the southern Nigeria pediment led by lieutenant colonel Hug Trenchard came into contact with the Tiv. Trenchard brought gifts for the tribal chiefs subsequently, roads were built and trade links established between Europeans and the Tiv. But before construction of roads began a missionary named Mary Slessor went throughout the region seeking to the people's needs. According to Gbor, the first contact with the Europeans was between the market traders and the first man that comes in contact with the Tiv was Dr W. B Baikie in 1854. He came through the River Benue and was going to Yola in search for a market place.⁷⁴

Moti and Wegh traced the contact of Tiv and the Europeans as a result of 1854-Baikie led Niger expedition into the then Northern Nigeria.⁷⁵ Utov comment that, not until 1907 the dream of Samuel Ajayi Crowther was realised when Dr. Karl Kumm founder of Sudan united mission (SUM) invited the South African branch of SUM to start work in Sudan especially in Nigeria.⁷⁶ The Christian message and eschatology greatly affected that of the Tiv. The missionaries attacked the socio-cultural ways of Tiv life. They were instrumental to the abolition of exchange marriage system of Tiv by the colonial governments in 1927. This means that the Tiv contact with the Europeans bring a total change of Tiv cultural values.⁷⁷

Gbenda assert that, the Europeans instigated what was called *Haakaa*-throwaway things (cultic objects). Anti-witchcraft movements were organised that culminated in the confiscation of sacred cultic emblems of the veneration of deceased ancestors in the spirits world.⁷⁸ Furthermore the missionaries frowned at Tiv music and material culture. The *akombo* and other spiritual forces used as intermediaries between man and unseen forces

were disrupted and rendered irrelevant in the new social order of the missionaries, more so, the use of *ilu* and *Indyer* (wooden drums in communicating to the invisible world is no longer common).

7. Tiv Sense of Community: Another renowned and significant influence exerted on the Tiv religion and values can be seen in Tiv sense of community. In a typical Tiv society, the individual and his obligations are reflected in the lives and fortunes of all other members of the society.⁷⁹ This explains that communalism gave way to individualism which is identified as European feature of life and family structure. In order to prevent members of the society from endangering the welfare of the Tiv land, elders who are the promoters and custodians of moral values enforce a code of conduct that manifests as taboos, prohibitions and laws. Fundamentally, moral values, like goodness, hospitality and law are not human aversions as such but enshrined in Tiv Religion.

The process of reviewing the Tiv morality of the past would amount to treating one moral norm or act to the other. However, the underlying principles of the review lie in the Tiv worldview. This world view is of hierarchical order whereby a chain linked the younger to the elder and ancestor. The chain led to a system of harmony that knit the Tiv society as an indivisible unitary society. Regrettably, this unitary form is gradually been eroded away, the consequence of such erosion is what we referred to as the morality of the modern Tiv society.

A reflection on modern Tiv morality is thus a reaction contrary to the Tiv morality of the traditional Tiv society. In this regard Katsina noted that; “A closer attention to the concept of Tiv morality on the present moral situation has shown that there is a sharp departure manifested in so many areas of our daily living ranging from communal crises, ingratitude, envy, jealousy to irresponsibility.⁸⁰ This situation was hither to unheard of and rightly a deviation from the unified system of a Tiv man whose slogan of *ayootutu ka u no? Ka se!* Was a railing call for solidarity, communality, and all the values that promote and sustain group mentality.

Responding to the contemporary morality of the Tiv society, Suemo Chia noted thus; we are a disgrace and in shambles economically, politically, socially, culturally and spiritually⁸¹. Commenting on the destruction done to the traditional methods of ensuring morality Okwueze said “modernisation is tradition smashing, which is to say, it has tended to destroy almost all the institutions traditionally employed to exercise control over morality.”⁸² From the foregoing above, it is very clear that Tiv religious cultures and traditions which is built in their religion have been tempered with through the emergence of Christian religion.

Recommendations

From the basic of findings discussed above, the study hereby makes the following recommendations:

(i). The Tiv cultural heritage and cherished traditional code of conduct that is systematically eroding away should be properly taught at all levels of education in Benue State to enable the younger generation to know about their past heritage and the need to sustain positive values.

(ii). Christianity in Tiv land should embrace Tiv traditional and cultural values for a meaningful dialogue in the on-going enculturation and for its continuous fast growth. This should be done by the systematic study of Tiv traditional religious beliefs and practices in all levels of education in Benue State.

(iii). The indigenisation of Christian names should be encouraged and not be seen by Christians as a protest against Christianity, but as part of the African’s search for cultural identity. Besides, indigenous names give their bearers some psychological satisfaction and fulfillment.

(iv). The Church should institute research into the nature, motives and circumstances of the polygamous tendencies among its members in Tiv land. Instead of condemning it outright specifically, the Church should find out against African (Tiv) background culturally whether polygamy as an institution is irrevocably, absolutely and irreconcilably opposed to the biblical data of the New Testament.

(v). The Church should not dabble into certain areas that have no bearing with religion; rather, they should concern itself with promotion of human conscience that is the pivot of personality development and political maturity.

(vi). The liturgy of the Church should be purged of elements that perpetuate the foreign culture, and the African theologians should take it as a function to re-adapt the doctrine of the Church to be relevant to African (Tiv) ways of life.

Conclusion

In view of the foregoing, the study states that the exploration of the fundamental principles which guide some aspect of Tiv culture reveals the effects of the social, religious and cultural change in Tiv tradition. In the traditional Tiv set up, before the cultural contact, it is observed that, their day to day life styles was accordingly influenced by the norms of ancestral cult; This is because of its dominant influence on the life of Tiv people. In this respect, that moral, social, political, economic life was subsequently ordered on the contrary as everybody is going about without following any norms of the society in the process of Christianisation, Westernisation and modernity, as a result, the cherished Tiv cultural values have been thrown to the background.

The modern Tiv society is generally surrounded by two apparent irreconcilable worlds. The traditional religiosity oriented world of their forefathers and the invading secular oriented worlds of their colonisers experienced in the form of western culture. The advent of Christianity in Tiv land has led to the invasion of the traditional religious practices and cultural values of the people. It has undermined the social and cultural practices that had been in existence, Christianity intended to destroy the evils associated with the practice of Tiv traditional religion, as a result of this advent, so many aspects of development have been affected.

This investigation shows several cultural values that can justify the reality that the Tiv have traditional values inherited from the forebears that have been put aside by imposition of foreign cultural structures which has contributed to the lost glory of the Tiv People of Central Nigeria. In this case, alien's structures have broken up the Tiv traditional family structures, community solidarity and oneness, and the general concept of the ancestral veneration and so on. The fact is that these cultural contacts exposed people to both positive and negative experiences. For instance, in the past, people were made to feel that their culture was inferior and they are to accept foreign values and ways of life. However, today, in all of Africa, especially in Tivland, there is the move towards cultural revival and that is where this study has fully emphasizes that "there should be much emphasis on Christianising Tiv cultures and traditions in this 21st century" in order to regain the lost glory that had been smashed for growth and development of the Tiv people.

The influence of Christianity on Tiv cultural values and traditional religion has tremendous effects on the Tiv worldview. As a result, this investigation has contributed in such a way that the Tiv are been sensitizes about the fundamental elements of their culture, which can be revived to enhance their progress and development. This work will serve among other things especially, on the documentation of Tiv tradition and also, offer some guiding principles for pastoral orientation of Tiv Church in the area of ecumenism and dialogue with Tiv cultural values. Through this study, perhaps, give a more concrete and practice analysis of the past and present situation with regard to the faith of the Christian adherents of Tiv could be of value towards improved understanding of some traditional concepts, in this respect, reduces the degree of syncretism among the converts to Christianity.

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